

Practical performance-based design of friction pendulum bearings for a seismically isolated steel top story spanning two RC towers

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Abstract

A case study of performance-based design is presented for a seismically isolated steel structure that rests on top of two adjacent high-rise reinforced concrete towers, the latter separated by means of an expansion joint. The isolation system comprises Friction Pendulum Bearings (FPBs) that are designed to accommodate two salient characteristics of the system. First, the isolated top floor is subjected to narrow-band floor acceleration histories as the ground motion excitation is filtered by the dynamic response of the supporting towers. Second, the displacement demands imposed to the FPBs are affected by the in-phase or out-of-phase movement of the supporting structures, with the latter case potentially giving rise to higher displacement capacity requirements for the bearings. In a search for a solution beyond conventional design norms, the probability of bearing failure associated with a wide range of FPB displacement capacities was determined via an explicitly risk-consistent performance-based seismic design. Overall, the case-specific design approach is shown to be able to meet any desired performance objective, consistently determining the final compromise between safety, cost-efficiency and practicability.

Keywords: Friction Pendulum Bearings, Performance-Based Seismic Design, Base Isolation, Nonlinear Analysis

1 INTRODUCTION

Buildings designed according to contemporary seismic codes, such as ASCE/SEI 7-16 (ASCE 2017) or EN1998 (CEN 2005), are typically built to satisfy requirements that reflect the lowest

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acceptable compromise between initial cost and potential loss of life in a building. Such buildings are generally meant to sustain moderate damage in a so-called design-level seismic event, i.e., an earthquake that has a probability of 10% in 50 years of being exceeded, yet without any global or local collapse, thus allowing safe evacuation of inhabitants without loss of life. At the same time, it is implied that the buildings will maintain structural integrity and, despite some local failures, will not globally collapse at higher intensities of typically unspecified magnitude.

The reason for such relatively high risk assumed by the owner, stems from the unspoken compromise that forms the basis of a seismic design code. This was never meant to serve the actual needs of all possible owners, but only provide a minimum standard of safety, in the same way that one may buy different quality cars, but they must all have at least some basic safety features (e.g., seat belts and frontal air-bags). For a risk-aware client and an expensive investment, this compromise may indeed be unfavorable and within the intensity-based design philosophy of the current seismic codes, only implicit adjustments are possible for dealing with such situations, such as assigning the structure to a higher importance (or consequence) class. This decision essentially results in increased seismic design actions at a given site but the improvement to the seismic performance of the final design is not explicitly assessed. In other words, we may know that we have improved the design, but we do not know by how much in terms of risk.

Relatively recent, the concept of performance-based earthquake engineering (Cornell and Krawinkler 2000, Krawinkler and Miranda 2004, Yang *et al.* 2009) has evolved to meet precisely such needs of interested stakeholders. It essentially allows tailoring a building to the user's needs to achieve any number of performance objectives in terms of risk rather than intensity. Thus, a building may be designed to sustain global collapse with a probability of exceedance lower than 1% in 50 years, equivalent to a Mean Annual Frequency (MAF) of $-\ln(1-0.01)/50 \approx 0.002\%$, and exceed moderate "life-safety" damages at a probability of 10% in 50 years or less, rather than having an unknown performance for both these limit-states when designed at the 10% in 50 years *intensity* level.

Base isolation is deemed to be an earthquake mitigation strategy that essentially aims at decoupling the structural motion from the ground shaking (Constantinou 1994, Makris 2019), via installing flexible or friction bearings at the base level of a structural system. Base-isolated buildings have long been believed to exhibit a superior seismic performance, with reduced accelerations and displacements, as opposed to conventional fixed-based buildings. However, recently, they were subjected to considerable criticism (e.g. Kitayama and Constantinou 2018)

for their inferior performance in seismic scenarios other than the ones they were designed for. In particular, in several cases, they were found to exhibit unacceptable “global collapse” (or more accurately bearing failure) probabilities mainly due to excessive displacement demands that could not be accommodated by the isolation devices (Erduran *et al.* 2011). Quite surprisingly, in many cases their performance was even worse than that experienced by non-isolated structures (Iervolino *et al.* 2018, Kitayama and Constantinou 2018).

In response to such evidence, conventional concepts in the design of base isolation systems have resulted in updated prescriptive formulas for the required displacement capacity of bearings. For example, Zayas *et al.* (2017) recommended having a total isolator displacement capacity (including the capacity of soft stops) of at least 1.5 times the displacement demand in the Risk-Targeted Maximum Considered Earthquake, MCE_R [typically defined to have an intensity 1.5 times higher than the design level of 10% in 50 years per ASCE/SEI 7-16 (2017)] and an isolator shear strength of at least 3.0 times the base shear in the MCE_R . In a similar vein, Kitayama and Constantinou (2018) suggest a bearing capacity of at least 1.8 times the minimum code-prescribed value in order to achieve the code-targeted reliability against global collapse when no displacement restrainers are provided.

The abovementioned requirements may be simple to implement but they are not tied to the site hazard characteristics or the structural behavior of the system, and thus may not deliver the desired levels of safety. In other words, although they can surely enhance seismic collapse performance, they inject an unknown safety margin to the isolated system that may be inadequate in some cases or uneconomical in others. Given that, compared to conventional buildings, isolated structures are by design relatively simple to model and analyze, an explicit consideration of risk is actually a viable alternative. All in all, by means of a case-study, this study provides a comprehensive step-by-step guide for undertaking a full risk-based design of base isolated buildings using the latest generation of record selection and response assessment tools.

2 IMPLICIT OR EXPLICIT RISK CONSIDERATION?

Performance-based seismic design is considered nowadays a well-established concept in earthquake engineering (Zareian and Krawinkler 2009, Aschheim *et al.* 2019). Upon its application, a structural system is designed such that its response does not exceed mandated thresholds with a MAF that is higher than a prescribed one. Hence, meeting an objective essentially means that the $x\%$ -confidence estimate (due to uncertainties) of the MAF, $\lambda_{x\%}$, of the demand, D , exceeding

the capacity, C , should be lower than the maximum MAF, λ_o , allowed for this limit-state (Vamvatsikos 2017):

$$\lambda_{x\%}(D > C) < \lambda_o \quad (1)$$

Values of $x = 0.5 - 0.9$ may be adopted to denote the severity of the consequences and protect against associated non-modeled uncertainties (Chapter 13, Aschheim *et al.* 2019). Demand and capacity are typically provided in terms of engineering demand parameters (EDPs), i.e., typical responses estimated by structural analysis, such as member forces/moments, interstory drifts or peak floor accelerations. Despite the aforementioned straightforward definition, the implementation of performance-based design is nontrivial in most engineering projects, as it may typically require several cycles of re-analysis and re-design until Eq. (1) is satisfied. Thus, the current state-of-practice favors an implicit risk-aware rather than an explicit risk-consistent application of the concept.

Prime examples of implicit “performance-based” methodologies are the current intensity-based design approaches, adopted by practically all contemporary design codes (Vamvatsikos *et al.* 2016). Therein, satisfying an objective is reduced to directly checking for a *conservative* estimate of the EDP demand exceeding an *unconservative* estimate of the capacity at a single given intensity level, this typically being $IM = IM_o$, or the intensity with an exceedance MAF of λ_o ,

$$D_{z\%}(IM_o) > C_{(1-w)\%} \quad (2)$$

λ_o is typically associated with an exceedance probability of 10% in 50yrs, while z , w are confidence levels that are meant to be higher than 0.5 and are implicitly (and imprecisely) imposed by modern codes through safety factors, characteristic (rather than expected) values of strength etc. Clearly, Eq. (2) is much simpler to evaluate than Eq. (1). Yet, the two are not mathematically equivalent; more importantly, Eq. (2) is not necessarily a conservative substitute. As shown, for example, by Katsanos and Vamvatsikos (2017) and Aschheim *et al.* (2019), its conservativeness is subject to vagaries that make it quite case-sensitive. Thus, intensity-based approaches may be risk aware, yet not risk consistent, since the probability of the structure exceeding a specific performance objective is never directly estimated. It is only indirectly accounted for via the return period of the ground motion intensity level.

More importantly, to remain within the realms of elastic analysis, intensity-based methodologies typically attempt to employ evaluations of Eq. (2) at a single hazard level of λ_o to imply that limit-states associated with much higher and rarer intensities are also satisfied. Thus, for a

structure to satisfy the collapse performance objective (often paired with a 1% probability of collapse in 50 years) it is implied that it is sufficient to test the structure at a design intensity with 10% probability of exceedance in 50 years. Last but not least, even when nonlinear response history analysis is performed, the design intensity spectrum is represented by a uniform hazard spectrum to which ground motion records are typically matched effectively ignoring the correlation among spectral values at different periods, and how this varies with intensity at any given site. Such simplifications that fully disregard the effect of response variability, structural nonlinearity and the shape of the seismic hazard curve (Vamvatsikos 2017) are unfortunately doomed to be either grossly conservative or grossly unconservative, with code committees rightfully aiming for the former.

A more elaborate, yet of questionable effectiveness, technique is the utilization in the design process of the risk-targeted design spectra that were adopted in ASCE 7-16 (ASCE 2017) in replacement of the uniform hazard spectra. These spectra have been appropriately calibrated for a wide range of structural typologies to help achieve the collapse performance target of 1% in 50 years and they are presently only available for USA territories (Luco *et al.* 2007). In particular, the methodology for obtaining a risk-targeted spectrum involves convolving the seismic hazard curve with a generic fragility curve that is deemed to be representative for the building stock in the considered country; by working backwards from a targeted 1% collapse probability in 50 years one may determine a new design spectrum that, if adopted in conventional design, will theoretically inject the required safety against collapse to any structural configuration. The use of the generic fragility functions is indeed the weak point of this approach, since apparently the variability of the building stock at the country level is difficult to depict by a single fragility. Moreover, it has been also demonstrated in the past that, even within the same building class, there is significant variability among the fragility/vulnerability curves of the index buildings that represent the class (Kazantzi *et al.* 2014). Using risk-targeted spectra for the seismic design of structures remains an implicitly risk-aware design methodology, since it cannot guarantee a uniform collapse risk across a range of structural designs. At best, risk-targeted spectra can offer risk harmonization among different types of buildings but certainly they cannot be used to target a specific risk value (Spillatura *et al.* 2019).

Contrary to the aforementioned implicit methods, a risk-consistent design assessment results in direct estimates of the EDP demand distribution and correspondingly the annual rate of exceeding a particular EDP level (Lin *et al.* 2013a, 2013b). In design terms, such an explicit risk-based approach aims at verifying for the designed structure that the risk of exceeding (i.e.,

violating) one or more limit-states does not exceed the target(s) specified by the code or agreed with the client, e.g. the risk of collapse not exceeding the target risk set to 1% probability of collapse in 50 years. The $x\%$ percentile estimate of the Mean Annual Frequency (MAF), denoted as $\lambda_{x\%}$, of the Demand, D , being greater than the Capacity, C , can be determined using the fragility-hazard convolution approach according to the Cornell *et al.* (2002):

$$\lambda_{x\%}(D > C) = \int_{IM} P(D > C | IM) |d\lambda(IM)| \quad (3)$$

Hiding within the above equation are the estimation of the MAF of exceeding given IM values, known as the hazard curve $\lambda(IM)$, as well as the assessment of the probability of demand exceeding a given capacity, termed the fragility curve $P(D > C | IM)$. The latter is a cumbersome operation that normally would need to be repeated for every new version of the structure being designed. Still, when the design parameter to be fine-tuned does not affect the structural behavior before violation of the limit-state, as is the case of Friction Pendulum Bearing (FPB) displacement capacity, this only needs to be done once. Hence, a fully risk-consistent design approach can be adopted for the case-study at hand without excessive computational demands. The selected methodology resulted in an entire solution spectrum, leading to a comprehensive discussion of safety versus cost alternatives and allowing the client to make an informed decision as to which collapse risk level fits her/his needs.

3 BUILDING DESCRIPTION

The case-study is a building complex in Nicosia, Cyprus, of six architecturally-distinct high-rise RC buildings that are separated, every two buildings, by expansions joints to essentially form three structurally independent building units (A, B and C, see Figure 1). The lateral load resisting system of the RC structures consists primarily of shear walls, mainly arranged along the transverse direction (Global Y, or top-to-bottom in Figure 1). At the top of building units A and B, which for modeling purposes have a height of 46.95m, rests a single-story base-isolated steel structure that is 5.5m high (see Figure 2). The base-isolation was used to protect the steel structure from the imposed seismic displacement demands, including the case of out-of-phase differential horizontal movement of the supporting structures. The bearings used for isolating the steel structure are friction pendulum bearings (FPBs) that according to the client's specifications have a reference radius of $R_{\text{eff}} = 318'' = 8077\text{mm}$ and a minimum friction coefficient of $f = 7\%$. The building complex was designed according to the provisions of Eurocode 8 (CEN 2005) for seismic loading. The main seismic design parameters are:

1. Soil type C
2. Importance class II (i.e., ordinary)
3. Medium Ductility Class
4. Behavior factor for RC towers: $q_x = q_y = 2.76$
5. Reference peak ground acceleration $a_{gR} = 0.20g$

Figure 1. Plan view of the Six Towers complex showing the three structurally independent building units.

Figure 2. Side view of the Six Towers building complex showing the three independent units and the location of the expansion/seismic joints.

4 SITE HAZARD

Accurate performance assessment requires accurate seismic hazard estimates. At present, the best available peer-reviewed seismic source model for Cyprus is the Earthquake Model of the Middle East (EMME2014) as described by Erdik *et al.* (2012). This incorporates a comprehensive model of the entire Middle East, complete with seismic mechanisms, rates, ground motion prediction equations and logic trees for handling uncertainty. Indicative results for the Eastern Mediterranean in terms of a 10% in 50 years peak ground acceleration hazard map appear in Figure 3. A single location at longitude 33.332 and latitude 35.222 within the city of Nicosia was employed to determine uniform hazard spectra (Figures 4a and 4b) and spectral acceleration hazard curves (Figures 5a and 5b). The former are shown for the 10% in 50 years Design Level Earthquake (DLE) and the 2% in 50 years Maximum Considered Earthquake (MCE) against their code-compatible counterparts. The corresponding EN1998-compatible MCE spectrum was also evaluated according to the ASCE 7-16 (ASCE 2017) provisions by multiplying the EN1998-compatible DLE spectrum (i.e., the design spectrum) by a factor of 1.5. The resulted spectra are relatively close to the spectra directly extracted from EMME2014 although the differences are non-negligible. Note that the vertical axis of Figures 4a – 4b are logarithmic, thus differences typically seem smaller than they actually are.

Figure 3. Reference Seismic Hazard Map of the Middle East depicting PGA levels with 10% probability of exceedance in 50 years (adapted from Giardini *et al.* 2016).

Figure 4. (a) 10% in 50yrs uniform (mean) hazard spectrum from EMME2014 for Nicosia soil type A versus the EN1998 design spectra ($a_g = 0.2g$) and (b) 2% in 50yrs uniform (mean) hazard spectrum from EMME2014 for Nicosia soil type A versus the EN1998 design spectra as augmented for MCE intensity level (PGA of $1.5 \times a_g = 0.3g$).

Finally, EMME2014 results are only available for rock sites, i.e., soil type A according to EN1998 (CEN 2005). To transform intensities from the implied bedrock to Soil C at the surface, where the foundation of the building complex lies, the spectral acceleration values were amplified by the ratio of EN1998 spectra for Soil C over those for Soil A at any given period. For the periods of interest, between 0.8sec and 2sec this resulted to amplification factors of ~ 1.7 . Obviously, there are better ways to effect such a transformation, yet this is the only one that retains some compatibility with the seismic code.

Ground motion selection was effected via the Conditional Spectrum (Lin *et al.* 2013a,b) approach using the Average Spectral Acceleration as the conditioning IM (Kohrangi *et al.* 2017). Lacking full disaggregation data for Nicosia, six different European sites were employed to select two ground motion sets of 30 records each that are hazard consistent with sites of medium (Kohrangi and Vamvatsikos 2016a) and high seismicity (Kohrangi and Vamvatsikos 2016b).

Figure 5. (a) $S_a(1.0s)$ hazard curve and (b) $S_a(2.0s)$ hazard curve for Nicosia soil type A from EMME2014.

5 STRUCTURAL MODELLING

5.1 Structural model

For investigating the seismic performance of the base-isolated steel structure that rests on the top of the RC tower units A and B, a 3D model was employed (Figure 6) using the OpenSees software platform (McKenna and Fenves 2001). The utilization of a 3D model as opposed to a 2D representation for the structures of interest was deemed to be more appropriate for depicting any torsional behavior under the seismic loading. Since we are interested in investigating the performance of the FPBs (or Friction Pendulum System bearings, FPS) rather than the already-designed building units, we need only reproduce their relative displacements under seismic loading. In particular, the structural model was constructed having in mind that it should be able to reproduce two salient features of the project at hand. The first is that the isolated steel structure rests on top of two towers and consequently it is subjected to narrow-band roof acceleration time histories, shaped by the filtering of the ground motion excitation through the supporting buildings. Thus, separate modeling of the building units is not an option. The second is that the two supporting towers have different modal characteristics, thus displacement demands imposed to the FPBs are mainly affected by their in-phase or out-of-phase movement. This requires accurately capturing the roof-level displacements and in-plane rotation of the towers, but not necessarily any lower-level displacements or interstory drifts.

As the two RC units are deemed to be flexible and ductile enough for the equal displacement rule to hold, while the steel top story is designed to remain elastic, an elastic model of the three building units is adequate for our purposes. This would not be possible, for example, in the case of a resonant top story isolated by elastomeric bearings, as the reduction in stiffness and associated period elongation resulting from any inelasticity in the RC towers could prove beneficial in collapse-level seismic motions. We should still expect some reduction of the narrow-bandness of the roof motions as inelasticity in the RC structures develops (Kazantzi *et al.* 2020). Nevertheless, this is expected to act beneficially or at least neutrally where no resonance is present, but certainly not against the conservativeness of the assessment.

Figure 6. Model of building units A & B and the base-isolated steel structure. The distance between the buildings was only employed for visualization purposes. The actual width of the expansion joint is incorporated in the connecting springs used at each floor to simulate the gap and the impact at closing.

Therefore, all structural elements were modelled as elastic beam-column elements, whereas for modelling the FPBs we employed the nonlinear Single Friction Pendulum Bearing element that is readily available in the element library of OpenSees. It incorporates 3D coupled friction properties consistent with a spherical concave sliding surface and a Coulomb friction model, while an initial elastic stiffness is provided before friction sliding commences. Rigid diaphragms were assumed at the floor levels to capture the effect of the concrete slabs. The floor mass (rotational and translational) was concentrated at the center of each floor diaphragm. The supports at the basement were assumed to be fixed whereas, the top of the basement (ground level) was restrained against lateral deformations. The lateral stiffnesses at each story in the two orthogonal directions of the modelled towers were appropriately calibrated to match the dynamic properties estimated via detailed design-grade RC tower models. A Rayleigh damping model was employed, assigning a damping ratio of 5% at the two fundamental translational modes of units A and B (Global X direction). Note that these two modes are indeed the ones that most contribute to the FPB deformations, while the 5% value is considered reasonable for elastic models of RC buildings under severe excitations. No Rayleigh damping was assigned to the FPB elements. Nevertheless, to take care of the mass-proportional damping we have calibrated by means of a sensitivity analysis the initial stiffness of the FPB elements. This calibration aimed to ensure that no excessive mass-proportional damping would appear to hinder the onset of sliding due to long period sliding modes.

Potential pounding due to closing of the seismic gap separating the towers was modeled by incorporating appropriate elastic perfectly-plastic gap elements with an allowable compression

gap of 0.5m. A relatively soft impact-spring stiffness was employed to avoid numerical instabilities, while only allowing sub-centimeter intrusion of one building into the other.

5.2 Modal characteristics

As already mentioned, given the mass of each floor, the stiffness of the building units was calibrated, so that the OpenSees model eigenvalues match as much as possible those of the detailed models used for design. The resulting eigenmodes are summarized in Table 1. Modes 1 and 2 essentially correspond to the static friction (initial stiffness) of the FPBs. Their actual period value is inconsequential to the analysis, as static friction is quickly overcome and the steel structure slides on top of the bearings. For reference, a nominal isolation period of $2\pi\sqrt{(R_{eff}/g)} = 5.7\text{sec}$ (per Mokha *et al.* 1991) may be estimated. Subsequent modes are of importance, especially the two dominant translational modes of vibration for each of the two considered building units in their X and Y global orthogonal directions. Translational modes of units A and B along the X-axis only mildly affect the isolated top story (Figure 7a-b) while the ones along the Y-axis are accompanied by horizontal rotation (“torsion”) of the isolated top story, as the two towers do not move in concert. All such influential modes and their periods are captured satisfactorily by the simplified model.

Table 1: Comparison of the first 12 periods of vibration evaluated using the 3D simplified OpenSees model and the detailed models that were used for designing the reinforced concrete structures. The fundamental mode shape for each building unit /direction appears in grey color and the second mode shape in orange.

Mode	Unit/Mode Description	Simplified model T [sec]	Detailed model T [sec]
1	Top Story / X Sliding	-	-
2	Top Story / Y Sliding	-	-
3	Unit A / X translation 1	2.114	2.114
4	Unit B / X translation 1	1.144	1.144
5	Unit B / Y translation 1 Top Story / Torsion	0.856	0.856 -
6	Unit A / X translation 2	0.769	0.745
7	Unit A / Y translation 1 Top Story / Torsion	0.582	0.582 -
8	Unit A / X translation 3	0.520	0.482
9	Top Story / Torsion	0.462	-
10	Unit B / X translation 2	0.452	0.475
11	Unit A / X translation 4	0.369	0.336
12	Unit B / Y translation 2 Top Story / Torsion	0.314	0.269 -

Figure 7. Fundamental mode shapes for each building unit /direction: (a) Mode 3, (b) Mode 4, (c) Mode 5 and (d) Mode 7, as depicted by means of the 3D OpenSees structural model.

5.3 Dynamic behavior

Building units A and B have a very distinctive behavior. Due to the arrangement of the shear walls perpendicular to the A-to-B axis (Figure 1), they are very stiff in the transverse direction (Global Y) while remaining relatively soft in the longitudinal direction (Global X). Thus, most of the deformation manifests as opening and closing of the seismic joint, with some pounding actually happening for very intense ground motions. Due to the low concavity of the sliding bearings, the top steel structure largely retains its initial position as the rooftops of units A and B displace below, mainly along the longitudinal X axis. It is this deformation of A and B that drives the bearing displacements, especially when they move away from each other. Figures 8 to 10 provide an example of the estimated rooftop and bearing deformation time-histories under the Hector Mine (1999) earthquake event, scaled to the 10% in 50 years intensity level. In particular, Figure 10 illustrates the FPB longitudinal displacement demands (Global X) evaluated at one corner of Building A (Figure 10a) and Building B (Figure 10b). The FPB displacement demands were evaluated as the difference between the relevant to the ground longitudinal displacements of either Building A or Building B and the relevant to the ground longitudinal displacement evaluated for the base isolated steel building. Figures 8 and 9 show the combined

effect of both the isolation system and the supporting buildings. Given the nonlinear modeling employed and the superposition of the responses, the “pure” equivalent isolation period of 5.7sec is observable mainly in the second half of the timehistories, where the buildings themselves undertake smaller deformations. Still, as Figure 10 shows, their vibration at shorter periods features heavily in the FPB demands at any time point.

Figure 8. Longitudinal displacements (Global X) at one corner of the roof of (a) Building unit A and (b) Building unit B versus the displacement of the corresponding supported point at the base of the isolated steel structure for the Hector Mine 1999, Tripp Flats record scaled to the 10% in 50 years level. All displacement values are relative to the ground. The difference of the values displayed in each figure reflects the displacement demand on the FPBs in the X direction.

Figure 9. Transverse displacements (Global Y) at one corner of the roof of (a) Building unit A and (b) Building unit B versus the displacement at the corresponding supported point at the base of the isolated steel structure for the Hector Mine 1999, Tripp Flats record scaled to the 10% in 50 years level. All displacement values are relative to the ground. The difference of the values displayed in each figure reflects the displacement demand on the FPBs in the Y direction.

Figure 10. FPB longitudinal deformation (Global X) at one corner of the roof of (a) Building unit A and (b) Building unit B for the Hector Mine 1999, Tripp Flats record scaled to the 10% in 50 years level. Both deformation time histories are determined from the corresponding displacement time histories of Figure 8.

6 SEISMIC PERFORMANCE ASSESSMENT

6.1 Collapse fragility assessment

The collapse fragility, i.e. the probability of the seismic demand exceeding collapse-level capacity limits given the seismic intensity, was evaluated by means of nonlinear response history analyses. Herein, the collapse capacity is solely determined by the maximum deformation capacity of the FPBs, disregarding the collapse capacity of the RC towers themselves. Such an approach is supported by the findings of the RINTC project (Iervolino *et al.* 2018), demonstrating that RC buildings designed according to EN1998 are in general much less susceptible to collapse compared to base-isolated structures. This may not hold for FPB deformation capacities that are well beyond the code-mandated ones, as may result from a performance-based design approach, yet even then it remains consistent with our focus on designing the FPBs on top of the already-designed RC towers. The derivation of analytical fragility curves via nonlinear dynamic analyses has been demonstrated in several past studies (e.g. Dymiotis *et al.* 1999, Kwon and Elnashai 2006, Kazantzi *et al.* 2011), whereas detailed guidelines for generating analytical seismic fragility curves of single structures are provided in Bakalis and Vamvatsikos (2018).

Nonlinear response history analyses were performed at both a moderate and a high intensity level by employing two ground motion sets that were carefully selected for European sites of moderate and high seismicity (Kohrangi and Vamvatsikos 2016a,b), each comprising 30 ground motion records times two horizontal components each. The peak FPB deformation regardless of direction (i.e. the peak value of the vector sum of instantaneous of X, Y deformations) was

employed to characterize demand. Spectral acceleration at a single period was the Intensity Measure (IM) of choice. More elaborate IM options are available in the literature (e.g. Bojorquez and Iervolino 2011, Kazantzi and Vamvatsikos 2015, Eads *et al.* 2016, Tsantaki *et al.* 2017), which can result in an enhanced (i.e., unbiased) seismic response mean and lower dispersion estimates. Still, given the state-of-art ground motion selection approach employed, it was considered unnecessary to adopt them for the case at hand.

Due to the flexible few first modes of Building unit A contributing most to the deformation demand, it was chosen to employ as conditioning period the 60/40 weighted mean of the first two structural modes, i.e., 2.114sec, and 1.144sec yielding a rounded value of $T=1.75\text{sec}$. The discrete data points in terms of the 5% damped spectral acceleration (geometric mean of the two horizontal components) and the maximum recorded FPB deformation were fitted via a power law regression line (Cornell *et al.* 2002), as shown in Figure 11. The results were employed to produce collapse fragility curves for a range of different FPB deformation capacities spanning between 0.3m and 1.5m, as shown for example in Figure 12 for a deformation capacity of 0.82m. An additional epistemic uncertainty dispersion (log-standard deviation) of 0.20 was assumed to account for unmodeled sources of uncertainty and infuse additional conservativeness. The overall collapse capacity dispersion thus becomes equal to 0.51.

Figure 11: Results from 60 nonlinear response history analyses in terms of the maximum FPB displacement versus the geomean value of $S_a(1.75\text{sec})$ at 5% damping. The red line represents the power law regression on the cloud of points.

Figure 12: The collapse fragility curve for the base isolation system when the bearings have a maximum deformation capacity of 0.82m.

6.2 Maximum displacement risk curve and option study

The hazard curve determined for $S_a(1.75\text{sec})$ (geomean component, 5% damped) was convolved with the collapse fragilities estimated for the FPBs. The resulting collapse risk curve appears in Figure 13. Based on these results, the following three options are delineated:

(a) Option 0: Conform to EN15129 (CEN 2009) and design the FPBs for a displacement capacity of 1.5 times the Design Level Earthquake (or 10% in 50 years) demand of 30cm, i.e., $1.5 \times 30\text{cm} = 45\text{cm}$. According to Figure 13, this will achieve a collapse risk of 5.2% in 50 years. This is considered unacceptable when compared to the implied safety of EN1998 (CEN 2005) designed non-isolated structures and it constitutes a clear failure of the EN15129 standard to provide adequate safety. This option is not recommended.

(b) Option 1: Target a collapse risk of 1% in 50 years. Then a bearing displacement capacity of 0.82m is required. This fully complies with the stated targets of ASCE/SEI 7-16 (ASCE 2017) for ordinary structures (Importance Class II or Risk Category II) and it approximately complies with the average implied safety of EN1998 conventional structures (Iervolino *et al.* 2018). This is considered the best compromise between cost and safety for this building, assuming installation of the enlarged isolators is possible given the available space at the rooftops of Buildings A and B. The introduction of fail-safe mechanisms (e.g., perimeter stoppers) can even further improve performance under rare ground motions.

(c) Option 2: Comply with SISCF requirements (Zayas *et al.* 2017) and target an improved collapse risk of 0.2% in 50yrs. This requires an FPB displacement capacity of 1.31m according to Figure 13. As recent results (Iervolino *et al.* 2018, Spillatura 2018) from the RINTC project

have shown, most EN1998-conforming structures (with the notable exception of precast RC buildings and EN15129-conforming isolated buildings) have collapse risk below 0.5% in 50 years, with this value increasing for regions of higher seismicity and buildings of larger height. This in fact supports increasing the safety of the isolation system to lower the collapse risk. Still, at such large intensities, the uncertainties involved in the near-collapse behavior of the supporting towers are too large to ignore. Thus, there is not sufficient confidence in the behavior of the two RC towers to support an even safer base-isolated top story. Therefore, the increased capacity of the bearings would be best taken advantage of by a redesign of building units A and B to a higher Importance Class.

As usually happens when a desktop theoretical/numerical analysis meets physical and fiscal reality, neither of the three options was adopted. Due to physical constraints, namely the size and weight of the bearings to be supported by an already designed reinforced concrete slab, a fourth option emerged to reach a practical compromise: FPBs with 65cm of displacement capacity and a 2% in 50 years exceedance (nominally “collapse”) probability plus some perimeter stoppers as a fail-safe mechanism in case of displacement capacity exceedance. Overall, this provided a far safer design than what the current code provisions mandate, while remaining within the sphere of practicality and realizability.

Figure 13. The FPB maximum displacement risk curve in terms of the PoE in 50years. The value of 0.82m corresponding to the 1% probability of exceedance is indicated by a red cross.

7 CONCLUSIONS

An explicit performance-based design methodology was demonstrated by means of a case study that involves a base-isolated top story steel building spanning two reinforced concrete towers. The risk-consistent design methodology adopted for designing the FPB isolators is believed to be superior to prescriptive performance-based approaches since: (a) it yields a risk-consistent structural design, (b) it does not inject unnecessary conservatism, resulting in more economical final design products, and (c) the collapse risk or any other targeted performance objective can be precisely tailored to the client's needs. The latter point became the focus of the project, as it essentially allowed entering meaningful discussions with the building owner and in-house engineers, leading to a joint agreement on the best compromise of safety and practicality that was realizable in a project that was already under way. Prescriptive intensity-based design approaches may be easier to implement, but they simply fail to reach such standards of quality, adaptability and verifiable safety.

Acknowledgements The authors would like to thank A. Antoniou (design engineer), K. Papanikolaou (quakeGuard Cyprus Ltd), and M. Karantzakis (ENKA Technologies) for providing the drawings, the design data and in-depth technical information for the structures. We would also like to thank M.C. Constantinou, R.O. Hamburger, K. Miyamoto, J. Eiding, R. Ludke, A. Wada, Y. Bozorgnia and V. Zayas for their constructive criticism and helpful discussions on collapse safety targets for buildings.

Funding Financial support has been provided by the European Commission through the Horizon 2020 programs “PANOPTIS–Development of a decision support system for increasing the resilience of transportation infrastructure based on combined use of terrestrial and airborne sensors and advanced modelling tools”, Grant Agreement number 769129, and “HYPERION–Development of a decision support system for improved resilience & sustainable reconstruction of historic areas to cope with climate change & extreme events based on novel sensors and modelling tools”, Grant Agreement number 821054.

COMPLIANCE WITH ETHICAL STANDARDS

Conflicts of interest The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest.

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